

Sustainable Development of Women through the Power of Sport

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to shed light on the development of women and girls and benefits they gain through participation in sports. Today sports and physical activity as a strategy for the empowerment of girls and women has been gaining recognition worldwide. Women could be empowered through education, sports and physical activities and by giving them equal opportunities in different walks of life. Through sports, women and girls can increase their confidence, self esteem and benefit from the other positive impacts sport has on health and psychosocial conditions. Irrespective of various reasons for less number of women participation in sport, women with their herculean efforts will have to challenge all the social hurdles to enhance their participation in sports. Government should implement suitable measures to invest in increasing the women's participation in sport as it has a key role to play in sustainable development of positive social and economic outcomes in a nation.

Keywords: Sports, Sustainable development, Empowerment

Introduction

Sport is perceived as “an essential empowering influence of sustainable development”.

Sport is an integral part of the culture of almost every nation. Sport adds to prosperity paying little heed to age, gender or ethnicity. It is enjoyed by all, and its reach is unrivalled. Sport has turned out to be a savvy and adaptable instrument for advancing harmony and advancement destinations. The growing contribution of sport to the sustainable development and empowerment of women, young people, individuals and communities as well as to health wellbeing, education and social inclusion objectives are exceedingly recognized.

The International Olympic Committee is comprehensively pushing for the advocating for the use of sport to: advance wellbeing and the aversion of non-transmittable maladies, accomplish quality education through values-based learning, promote gender equality, strengthening of young girls and women, add to tranquil and peaceful social orders and to develop human capital and human potential (IOC, 2016).. Game regularly gives safe situations at the grassroots and network levels, at which members are united in the quest for common objectives and premiums; learn values of respect, resistance

and reasonable play; and create social capabilities. As a common denominator and shared passion, sports can fabricate connections between communities regardless of their cultural differences or political divisions. In the midst of contention or unsteadiness, donning exercises can furnish sportspersons with a feeling of commonality (Sport for Development and Peace International Working Group, Right to Play, 2008).

Role of Sport in Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals

To achieve gender equality by 2030, the leaders from all over the world accepted and followed the agenda for sustainable development in 2015.

The Agenda explicitly recognizes sport as an important enabler for development and women's empowerment (Scoring for gender equality through sport, 2017). Sports participation empower girls and women to acquire health information, skills, social networks, and leadership experience; and help develop skills in management, negotiation and decision-making girls to become leaders in the workplace, in the home and in all areas of community life. A survey of executive women found that 80% played sports in their youth; 69 % said sport contributed to their professional success (Harnessing the Power of Sport for Peace and Development, 2014). Women involvement in sports can make a significant contribution to public life and community development (Surender, 2017). Women's participation in sport can create a substantial contribution to social life and tradition development.

Sports as a means of Women Empowerment

Kiran Bedi quotes that the two key pillars of upbringing of women are sports and education.

Adolescent girls and young women are powerful agents of change. Empowered women will grow into a strong leader, when she is given a chance. The prosperity of girls and women is necessary for a fair and prosperous world (Sports and SDG, 2017). Bobenrieth states that girls are born leaders, sport is one of the opportunity to practice the leadership qualities.

Sport can engage and offer young women a spot to create abilities and information that convert into life off the field. Game in its easiest structure empowers adjusted cooperation and has the ability to advance and accomplish gender uniformity inside social orders. Through game and physical activities, ladies can be empowered, increment their certainty and advantage from the other positive effects sport has on wellbeing and psychosocial conditions (Global games .com, Feb, 2017).

Benefits of Sports Participation for Women

Sports involvement can play a significant role in promoting the physical and mental wellbeing of women. Experts agree that involvement in sports and physical activity can potentially offer a wide range of life benefits for women. Various research proved that through involvement in an organized sports , the young girls get a better, healthier and a successful life.

Regular exercises and participation in sports activities is associated with a longer and better quality of life, reduced risks of a variety of diseases and many psychological and emotional benefits (Abney and Richey, 1992). Brady and Kahn (2002) suggested a positive relationship between physical activity and a host of factors affecting girls' physical health, including diabetes, blood pressure and the ability to use fat for energy. Teenage sports participation may help prevent osteoporosis by increasing the bone mass and might provide some protection from developing osteoporosis later in life. A study by Robert Kaestner (2010) showed that girls who participated in athletics have a 7-percent lower risk of obesity 20 to 25 years down the road.

A position statement of the International Society of Sport Psychology (2009), drew out numerous mental health benefits of physical activity. Physical activity can contribute to the reduction of

problematic levels of anxiety, neuroticism, various kinds of stress and depression by acting as anti-depressants and psychotherapy (Singer, 2002). Compared to non athletes, female athletes not only excel in academics, but also fine tune their leadership, collaboration and communication skills showed a study by the women's sports foundation (2015).

A survey by EY's Women Athletes Business Network & ESPN (2014) reported that nearly 74% among 400 adult women, agreed that their career gets accelerated by playing sports and 61% showed themselves as real proof of sports contribution to their success in career.

Several researches have showed that, sports help women to showcase their talents, skills and abilities to the society who thinks women as a weaker sex. Women sportspersons acquire self-esteem and self-confidence, creates merits of inspiration, faith, hope and courage via sports participation. Sport also offers opportunities for social interaction and friendship, which can raise awareness of gender roles among male counterparts and convey social and psychological benefits to both individuals and groups. Women who play sports or participate in physical activities have a more positive body image, build life skills and may create social networks than women who do not participate (Surender, 2017).

Sports Participation of Women in India

A few Indian ladies have partaken in the Olympics before. In India, sportswomen are on an ascent at national and global dimension - Sindhu, Sania Mirza, Mary Kom, Saina Nehwal, Mithali Raj, Dipika Pallikal, Geeta Phogat, Sonika Kaliraman and numerous others had brought laurels to our nation. Disregarding sufferings in the male dominated sports arena, society's expectations and censures, they have endured and are presently motivating ladies' support in games as well as expanding the fame of the specific games itself.

Conclusion

“Sports: A Powerful Strategy to Advance Women's Rights.”- Astrid Aafjes.

Presently, women take an interest expertly in each game at institutional, national and universal dimension by resisting the social and mental odds, yet there is still a great deal to be accomplished. Young women all over the world get fewer chances, less speculation, training and safety when they play sport. When they make it as expert competitors, they meet the unattainable rank and a considerable pay hole (IOC, 2016). There might be number of explanations behind less number of ladies participation in game. Indeed women should test all the social obstacles with their massive endeavors to improve their participation in games. For the sustainable development of a country, strengthening of women in all fields particularly sport ought to be perceived. Henceforth more measures should be taken by government to increase and improve women's participation in sports.

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